

Identification of manmade disasters in Kerala ‘Stray Dog Menace in Kerala

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ABSTRACT

In Kerala stray dog menace is emerging as a major problem. Around 1.84 lakh people are attacked by stray dogs. There are around 2, 68,994 stray dogs in Kerala. This study is tries to find out the emerging manmade disaster, its important, reasons, problems and solutions etc.,. This study is a descriptive study, data are collected from the newspapers and websites etc.,. The stray dogs are increasing every year in Kerala, the reason for increasing the number is the lack of waste management system,. Domestic dogs without licence, illegal butchery and meat selling, emerging service sectors, etc.,. And the problems due to this are : rising number of stray dogs, increased number of dog bites, domestic animals are attacked and killed by stray dogs, government cannot make proper measure to control this, conflict between animal lovers and state government, health hazards due to dog bites, in availability of vaccine, legal issues, etc.,. And its solutions are proper waste management system, provide pre-exposure prophylaxis vaccines for rabies, Implement strict laws for domesticating animals: make strict laws regarding domestic animals. Systematic sterilization, vaccination and community level adoption of dogs for effectively reducing dog population and aggression in dogs, and eliminating the risk of rabies. Make local self-governments more responsible and provide measure for control stray dog menace, aware community, and proper waste management etc. Thus the study states that stray dog menace is an emerging manmade disaster because the state government is facing problems to solve stray dog menace due to the strong opposition from the animal lovers. So the people are fear about the spread of rabies through stray dog bites, and the safety of the people who live in Kerala is at risk. So this is a manmade disaster.

Keywords: Manmade disaster, Manmade disaster, Sterilization, ABC – Animal Birth Control Programme.

INTRODUCTION

According to UN Disaster management training programme – A disaster is a serious disruption of the functioning of a society, causing widespread human material or environmental losses that exceed the ability of the affected society to cope using only its own resources. The word disaster is from a French word ‘Desastre’ meaning bad or evil. A disaster can be either natural or manmade, Natural disasters are: Flood, Cyclone, Drought, Earthquake, Cold wave, Thunderstorms, Mud slides, Storm, Tsunami etc., and manmade disasters are Setting of fires, Epidemic, Deforestation, Pollution due to prawn cultivation, Chemical pollution, Wars, Road/train accidents, Food poisoning, crisis, industrial accident, fire, bomb explosions, nuclear explosions etc.,

- ❖ In the Kerala context the major disasters are tsunami, mud slides, flood, earthquake, storm, deforestation, chemical pollution, road and train accidents etc, in the recent years the stray dog menace emerged as the one of the problem faced by the people of Kerala. Thus this study is trying to state that stray dog menace is an emerging manmade disaster in Kerala. Major objectives of the study are:
- ❖ To consider the rising number of stray dogs and attacks on human and animals in Kerala as a manmade disaster which is emerged in recent period.

- ❖ To find out the reasons for the increased stray dog menace.
- ❖ Problems due to the stray dogs.
- ❖ Challenges for implementing stray dog control programme in Kerala.
- ❖ Find out solutions for the stray dog menace.

Methodology of research

This study is a descriptive study, here the researcher, describes about the recent problem faced by the Kerala community due to the increased number of stray dogs and their attacks. Data is collected from the newspapers and websites etc.,

Reasons :

- (1) **Careless waste disposal methods:** The urban environment in India has two features that they encourages stray animal population and exposed garbage and slums. In Kerala both in rural and urban areas there is no proper waste management system. Public and the civic bodies are partially responsible for the issue. One of the main reasons for the increase in stray dog numbers is the careless waste disposal methods.
- (2) **Illegal butchery and meat selling:** In Kerala mainly in rural areas there are many illegal meat selling are functioning. Thus the stray dogs found the food from the road sides where meat waste as dumped as sacks by

poultry traders and meat shops.

- (3) **Abandoned domestic dogs in the public places:** In Kerala most of the houses have one dog. Owners may also abandon their animals in the streets when they no longer want them.
- (4) **Domestic dogs without licence:** In Kerala most of the domestic dogs have no licence, and no proper vaccination. These leads to spread of rabies and other health problems.
- (5) **Emerging service sectors :** Due to the development there are emerging many food making entrepreneurship like hotels, catering services, home based food making etc. In these businesses there is no proper waste management system. So the stray dogs are getting attracted to the garbage dumped in the front of hotels and in compound.
- (6) No data in the government sector to identify the number of dead dogs and domestic dogs.

Problems

- ❖ **Increasing the number of stray dogs in Kerala:** the number of stray dog in Kerala is increasing every year. Most of the houses have one dog, but most of them have no licence and not vaccinating on time. As per the livestock census, there are 7, 17,899 male dogs and 2, 05,460 female dogs in Kerala, taking the total number of dogs to 9, 23,359. And there are 2, 68,994 street dogs of which 2, 33,483 are in rural areas and 35,511 in the urban streets. Experts say the number of street dogs would rise two-fold every year and the number of street dogs in Kerala would be more than 1 million in 2015. The practice of abandoning unwanted puppies and dogs in the street accelerates the population growth of stray dogs.
- ❖ **Increasing the number of stray dog bites:** According to a conservative government estimate at least 1.84 lakh people were menaced by feral dogs last year. They included infants, women, students, pedestrians, senior citizens, early morning walkers and two-wheeler riders. Feral dogs also attacked an unknown number of livestock and poultry. Rural communities suffered most. The loss to society in terms of working days and medical expenses was unquantifiable.
- ❖ **Domestic animals are attacked and killed by stray dogs in various places in Kerala :** stray dogs are also attacks domestic animals. There are many domestic animals are attacked and killed by stray dogs. It is mainly in rural areas.
- ❖ **State governments cannot implement proper measures to control this issue:** The state government cannot implement proper measures to control the stray dog population due to the strong opposition from the animal welfare board and animal lovers against the government decision to cull rabid and dangerous stray dogs state government cannot implement proper measures to control stray dog menace. In an all party meeting chaired by chief minister Oommen chandy entrusted local self government institutions with the task. Kerala Panchayati raj (licence of pigs and dogs) rules 1998 had been formulated by the government to minimize incidents of stray dog attack. And section 438 of the Kerala municipality and corporations act empowered the local bodies to seize stray dogs in their respective areas. Different district Panchayaths has initiated a comprehensive projects to tackle stray dog menace. And local self-governments are planning few ways to control stray dogs, these are: dog culling, Animal birth control programme (ABC) and exporting dog meat to northern states and other countries, which consume dog meat. But the Animal welfare board and animal lovers are against the decision of local and state governments regarding stray dog menace. Animal welfare board of India (AWBI) has warned the state government that its decision to cull aggressive street dogs would amount to contempt of Supreme Court.
- ❖ **Conflict between state government and Animal welfare board:** One of the problems facing while implementing stray dog controlling measures is the emerging conflict between the state government and animal welfare board and animal lovers. against the government decision to cull rabid and dangerous stray dogs state government cannot implement proper measures to control stray dog menace. The different district Panchayaths has initiated a comprehensive project to tackle stray dog menace. And also few more plans such as dog culling, Animal birth control programme (ABC) and exporting dog meat to northern states and other countries, which consume dog meat. But the animal welfare board and animal lovers are against the local government's decisions on controlling stray dog. Animal activists are incensed over the idea of exporting dog meat as a one-stop measure for curbing the state's stray dog population they say it is illegal to do so. NG Jayasimha a member of the animal welfare board of India has written to M.K Muneer, the state minister for Panchayaths and social welfare, seeking to advice the local self-governments to implement animal birth control programme than resorting to illegal, unscientific and illogical ideas such as trade in dog meat. And in recent days there was a large campaigning in social media against the state government's decisions on stray dog population control. They conducted a rally in Kolkata on July 27, 2015, called Boycott Kerala Worldwide protest against the Kerala governments plan to kill stray dogs.
- ❖ **Stray dogs bite causes to health problems:** Stray dog bites causes to health issues like rabies. Rabies is a major health problem causes due to the rabid dog's bite. Due to the increased stray dog attack the community people are in fear of spreading rabies. And they are insecure especially school children, women, etc.,. In the year 2014-15 there are 1.84 lakh bites reported and average rabies death is 60. Kerala annually spends more money Rs 8crore on rabies vaccination and serum than it on anti-cancer.
- ❖ **Inavailability of providing rabies vaccine:** The government health sector is not capable of providing rabies vaccine properly. In Kerala there are around 1.84 lakh animal bites annually. But due to the increased number of dog bites there is no enough vaccine in the government sector. Kerala annually spends more money Rs 8 crore on rabies vaccination and serum. Than it does on anti-cancer drugs. This is however, a far cry from what the government used to spend on the same in 2009, which was 36 crore. The treatment rationally comes in to question when the state

faced an acute shortage of anti-rabies serum. This year because of excessive demand.

❖ **Legal issues:** The laws that regarding animal rights is a reason for facing problems in culling and removal of dogs. The laws regarding these are: Section 11 of the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Act makes all animal cruelty a criminal offence. And Under Stray Dog Management Rules 2001, it's illegal for an individual, RWA or estate management to remove or relocate dogs. The dogs have to be sterilized and vaccinated and returned to the same area. Vaccinated and sterilized dogs cannot be removed by the municipality too. The Supreme Court of India in 2009 gave a similar stay order against removal culling or dislocation of a dog anywhere in India.

❖ **Steady increase in the number of accidents caused by dogs:** there has been a steady increase in the number of accidents caused by stray dogs. More than 150 deaths are reported from across the state every year.

Thus the stray dog menace is a significant problem in Kerala. More than 1.84 lakhs of people are bitten by stray dogs and around 60 persons are died due to rabies, per year in Kerala. The state government is facing major issues for implementing appropriate measures for solving this issue. So this problem is continuing and people are afraid of stray dogs and the rabies, killing of dogs is not possible thing and the results of Animal birth control programme, it take lot of time to complete and get result. At present safety of the people living in the Kerala is at risk. Here the researcher states that the stray dog menace is a Man Made Disaster.

Solutions

❖ **Proper waste management system and strict laws in the state:** One of the major solutions for stray dog population control is implementing a proper waste management system in the state. Removal or killing of stray dogs is not possible for controlling stray dogs because the sustain dog population is unchanged. Dogs are territories each one lives in its own specific area. When they are removed or killed the food source is still available. So dogs from other area will enter the vacant area. So waste disposal is the best way for controlling stray dog population. Stop throwing the garbage to the public. Responsible waste management system is the one of the ways to control the stray dog menace. And give severe punishments to the people who throwing waste to public places.

❖ **Pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) vaccines for rabies:** Provide pre-exposure prophylaxis vaccines for rabies,

especially for children. Include it in to the immunisation schedule of children. It is a strategy encouraged by the World Health Organization in areas where canine rabies is a major public health problem.

❖ **Implement strict laws for domesticating animals:** Make strict laws regarding domestic animals. Issue licence for all dogs. And certificates for their owner ship and death. And give punishments when violating these laws.

❖ **Systematic sterilization, vaccination and community level adoption :** One of the another solution for controlling stray dog menace is the systematic sterilization, vaccination and community level adoption of dogs.

❖ **Make local self-governments more responsible** and provide measure for control stray dog menace, give awareness to the community about importance of taking licence for dogs, sterilization and vaccination of dogs, and proper waste management etc.

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